

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) of g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2.3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N, 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Rapid generation advance of photoperiod-sensitive rice crosses under field conditions

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We evaluated segregating generations of Pankaj/Patnai 23 and Nagra 14-41/NC1281, two photoperiod-sensitive crosses intended for lowland conditions, for twice-yearly generation advance under field conditions. Patnai 23 and Nagra 14-41 are photoperiod-sensitive varieties, NC1281 is strongly photoperiod-sensitive, and Pankaj is a long-duration rice with weak photoperiod sensitivity.

The F₂ and F₄ populations were sown on 3 Jul and transplanted on 25 Jul in 1982 and 1983. Heading date, panicle length, and plant height were noted for each plant that flowered by 7 Nov. Four filled grains collected from each F₂ plant constituted the F₃ population. F₃ seeds

were sown 12 Dec 1982 and transplanted on 7 Feb 1983. Heading date was recorded until 10 Jun, and four seeds per plant were harvested to grow the F₄ population. F₂ plants that flowered after 10 Jun were not included in the study.

Panicle initiation in the photoperiod-sensitive varieties occurred when day length was less than 11 h 58 min, which was in Sep-Oct in Chinsurah (22° 52'N). Short day length extended from Sep to Mar. The Nov/Dec sowing flowered early. Thus, seeds from the F₂ population were advanced in dry season as the F₃ population. Twelve percent of the F₂ plants and 36% of the F₃ from Nagra 14-41/NC1281 did not flower by 10 Jun. However, all progeny of Pankaj/Patnai 23 flowered appropriately in both seasons.

The above findings show the feasibility of advancing lowland/deepwater crosses by advancing 2 generations a year in the field. □

Distribution of panicle length and plant height in F₂ and F₄ of two crosses, West Bengal, India.

	Distribution (% of population)			
	Pankaj/Patnai 23		Nagra 14-41/NC1281	
	F ₂	F ₄	F ₂	F ₄
Panicle length ^a (cm)				
15-19	0	0	0	0
20-24	55	67	40	34
25-29	41	33	58	61
30-34	3	0	2	5
Mean	(24)	(24)	(26)	(25)
Plant height ^b (cm)				
100-119	22	34	2	28
120-139	41	42	56	52
140-159	31	23	40	20
160-169	6	1	2	0
Mean	(135)	(127)	(135)	(132)

^a Av panicle length: Pankaj, 28 cm; Patnai 23, 25 cm; Nagra 14-41, 24 cm; NC1281, 27 cm. ^b Av plant height: Pankaj, 114 cm; Patnai 23, 138 cm; Nagra 14-41, 137 cm; NC1281, 139 cm.